

Does Chief Executive Officer Power Change the Impact of Sustainable Development Information Disclosure on Financial Performance?

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Abstract

Background: The disclosure of information on sustainable development is an issue that has garnered the attention of researchers and is a concern to society. Therefore, research on this issue is a crucial area of inquiry.

Objective: The study aimed to assess the influence of sustainable development information disclosure (SDID) on economic performance and to investigate whether chief executive officers (CEOs) modify the impact of sustainability disclosure on financial performance (FP) in an emerging economy.

Methodology: This research utilised a dataset compiled from annual reports and financial statements of 311 listed firms on the HCMC Stock Exchange (HOSE) and the Hanoi Stock Exchange (HNX) for the period 2020-2023. The Pooled OLS model was employed after performing a regression analysis using 2SLS to address the endogeneity problem and test the hypotheses proposed in the study.

Result: The study found no evidence of the effect of SDID on financial performance, as measured by ROA. However, when CEOs have expertise in finance and accounting, sustainable development information increases financial performance.

Conclusion: The results indicate that CEOs with strong knowledge and skills in finance and accounting play a significant role in enhancing the positive impact of sustainability disclosure on financial performance.

Unique contributions: This study represents an initial investigation in Vietnam to assess the influence of SDID on financial performance, with CEO power acting as a moderating variable in this relationship. It contributes to the existing foundational theory on the important role of CEO power in enhancing SDID while improving financial results in an emerging economy.

Key Recommendations: Future studies should further assess the impact of factors related to climate change, carbon emissions, political institutions, and other CEO characteristics on sustainability disclosure and financial performance to explore this issue in more detail.

Keywords: CEO, sustainable development information disclosure, financial performance, Vietnam

Introduction

In the context of sustainable development, the disclosure of sustainable development information is a crucial issue that is increasingly becoming a top concern on the agenda and of interest to investors, management agencies, and business units themselves (Lee & Hooy, 2024). The sustainable development of companies has an important contribution of information on environment, social, and governance in achieving long-term success goals through promoting better corporate governance mechanisms (Lee & Hooy, 2024). SDID is a useful tool to reduce information asymmetry, meeting the growing demand for transparency (Martínez et al., 2016). At the same time, SDID mitigates the disparity in information and reduces agency costs (Chen et al., 2023). Sustainability information is utilised by companies to connect with society and the environment, engaging stakeholders to gain social acceptance and increase stakeholder confidence in the company's sustainable growth (Alsayegh et al., 2020). Firms with profit maximisation strategies believe that non-financial disclosure increases costs, but some studies suggest that non-financial disclosure, such as SDID, increases reputation (Tan et al., 2020), increases firm value (Chen et al., 2023; Aras & Kazak, 2022); and reduces costs and risks (Tahmid et al., 2022). Meanwhile, Lee and Hooy (2024) argue that non-financial disclosure, such as SDID, provides growth opportunities but will expose firms to profit-related risks. However, in addition to the goal of maximizing profits, companies are facing the challenge of implementing SDID by regulations due to pressure and information needs from stakeholders and Stakeholder theory holds that for a business to achieve its profit goals, it must pay attention to the needs of its stakeholders (Velte, 2017). Furthermore, in addition to creating value for shareholders when conducting business activities, enterprises also have the responsibility to protect stakeholders' interests (Freeman, 1984), so SDID is a concern when investors make business investments. Therefore, SDID is considered a tool that contributes greatly to increasing corporate value (Feng & Wu, 2023).

The relationship between SDID practices or disclosures of corporate social responsibility information and FP or firm value has been widely explored in different studies before. Studies confirmed that SDID has the potential to improve the value of the entity because it brings long-term benefits to the company and contributes to risk reduction (Artamevia et al., 2024). Some studies suggest that SDID may enhance the value of the business and increase FP (Chang & Lee, 2022; Wu et al., 2022; Duan et al., 2023; Chen et al., 2023). In addition, a relationship between FP and SDID was found (Tahmid et al., 2022; Habib, 2023). Meanwhile, the upper echelons theory suggests that CEOs have a significant impact on disclosure related to CSR. CEOs have a key position in making strategic decisions for the firm, so the personal characteristics of the CEO can

impact ESG disclosure (Chu et al., 2023). CEO power indicates the extent to which an individual has influence and control over strategic decisions regarding information disclosure. Many studies acknowledge that CEO power influences social responsibility disclosure activities differently in developed markets compared to emerging markets, due to differences in governance structures and institutions. Powerful CEOs in developed economies are encouraged to disclose more information about social responsibility to maximize personal benefits, build better images (Li et al., 2018), and enhance their reputation (Barnea & Rubin, 2010). However, in emerging markets, powerful CEOs disclose less information about social responsibility because excessive SDID increases costs, reduces profits, and thereby affects the interests of shareholders and themselves (Barnea & Rubin, 2010). Or as Chu et al. (2023) provided evidence that companies with powerful CEOs tend to disclose less sustainability information, but Li et al. (2018) argued that influential CEOs increase the impact of SDID on profitability and increase FP.

Thus, numerous studies have been conducted on the impact of SDID on FP and the effect of CEO regulatory power on financial performance in developed countries, yielding inconsistent research results. Meanwhile, in Vietnam - - a country with an emerging economy, research on this issue is still quite limited, especially in the context of examining the regulatory role of CEO power on the relationship between SDID and FP, so a more comprehensive analysis is needed to assess how CEO power can change the impact of SDID on firm performance in a developing country to clarify the driving forces behind this relationship. Thus, the objective of this study is to assess how CEO power affects the relationship between the level of sustainability disclosure and financial performance, thereby providing a more theoretical foundation and a more comprehensive picture of the impact of SDID on FP. This study provides empirical evidence on whether SDID creates more value for firms where CEOs have greater power. Furthermore, our findings will have practical implications and guide CEO selection and evaluation, thereby enhancing the impact of SDID on FP.

Following the introduction, the next section of the article addresses the underlying theory and research hypotheses. The third part of the article is the research methodology. After that, the results and discussion are in the fourth part. The last part of the article presents the conclusions and policy implications.

Basic Theory and Research Hypotheses

Background theory

Various theories have been employed to explain the effect of published information about sustainability on performance, as well as whether CEO power moderates this relationship. The first is the stakeholder theory (Freeman, 1984), which posits that enterprises need to account for the interests of different stakeholders (including the interests of employees, customers, suppliers, policymakers, and environmental activists) rather than focusing solely on shareholders while making decisions. Companies must ensure that they carry out SDID activities in alignment with the values of their stakeholders. However, the interests of stakeholders are not homogeneous, so managers must deal with these conflicts of interest. Disclosing useful information that is relevant to all stakeholders is an optimal solution. Stakeholder theory suggests that the positive reputational impact of SDID strategies can accumulate only to a certain extent until the firm satisfies the desires

of its stakeholders (Freeman, 1984). Consequently, many studies recognise the positive effect of SDID on firm value (Chen et al., 2023; Aras & Kazak, 2022). Next is the agency theory, which also argues that conflicts of interest or increased agency costs exist because managers often prioritise personal interests over those related to shareholders in their decision-making (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). Therefore, to reduce these costs, shareholders require managers to provide more information to facilitate effective monitoring of operations. Meanwhile, the voluntary disclosure theory is used to explain why companies voluntarily disclose non-financial information. Companies disclose information voluntarily to enhance their reputation and credibility with stakeholders, as well as to reduce information asymmetry with them. In addition, signalling theory suggests that companies that disclose SDID information imply that they are engaging in environmental protection strategies, as they have an incentive to inform shareholders and stakeholders (Habib, 2023). These positive signals create attractiveness to investors. Meanwhile, legitimacy theory suggests that corporate social responsibility reporting provides information that legitimises behaviour to influence stakeholders and ultimately demonstrates social acceptance of the company (Habib, 2023).

The effect of SDID on financial performance

Research on SDID and FP has been conducted for an extended period (Orlitzky et al., 2003), but the current focus on sustainability performance has attracted numerous academic studies to investigate the influence of SDID on corporate value (Gillan et al., 2021; Velte, 2017). Nonetheless, specific investigations acknowledge that SDID negatively influences firm value or FP. Some studies indicate a positive association between SDID and FP or corporate value. Typically, stakeholder theory suggests that SDID can help increase corporate value by enhancing operating profits through relationships with stakeholders (Orlitzky et al., 2003). Habib (2023) acknowledges that SDID determines firm performance, helps firms enjoy a low cost of capital, does not suffer financial distress, and thus increases FP. Chen et al. (2023), and Aras and Kazak (2022) argue that SDID positively affects firm value by affecting Tobin's Q, and it impacts firm value as a whole and as separate factors (Tahmid et al., 2022). However, the opposing view argues that a firm's managers are involved in SDID to create their own benefits (Barnea & Rubin, 2010), which increases agency costs, and SDID investments lead to inefficient resource allocation away from productive projects. Therefore, SDID has a negative influence on corporate value (Groening & Kanuri, 2013). However, in the author's opinion and in an emerging market like Vietnam, allocating resources to SDID activities reduces operating efficiency. It reduces corporate value, so we propose the hypothesis as follows:

H1: There exists a negative relationship between the level of SDID and financial performance.

The moderating role of CEO power

Research on the impact of SDID on corporate value has received considerable attention, but empirical results have shown a great deal of conflict (Gillan et al., 2021). This may explain the presence of additional variables that influence the relationship between SDID and FP. Senior management support is an internal factor that may influence SDID (Chu et al., 2023). The CEO, as a key decision-maker, plays a crucial role in advancing sustainable practices and ensuring transparency in disclosures. An influential CEO exerts significant influence and authority over business management activities (Chu et al., 2023) and has a strong impact on SDID activities,

demonstrating their dedication to stakeholders (Li et al., 2018). CEOs with more experience tend to reduce institutional pressure by disclosing more sustainable information; thus, CEOs with higher power would lead to greater pressure to disclose sustainable information. Highly educated CEOs with prestige strengthen their position and power (Artamevia et al., 2024). So, this article analyses whether the variable of CEO power influences the association between SDID and financial performance. Li et al. (2018) suggest that the relationship between CSR disclosure and financial performance is significantly enhanced in the presence of CEO power. The author also agrees that CEO power can change the influence level of SDID on FP, so the hypothesis is proposed as follows:

H2: CEO power changes the effect of SDID on FP

Research Method

The paper aims to assess the impact of SDID factors on firm value and evaluate how the power of the CEO moderates the effect of SDID on FP in Vietnam. The dataset is collected from 311 non-financial enterprises listed on HOSE and HNX between 2020 and 2023. After excluding companies with insufficient data over 4 years and financial institutions (due to their different financial reporting structures), the final sample comprises 311 companies with 1,243 observations. The starting point for the research period is 2020, as this year Vietnam issued Circular 96/2020/TT-BTC, which regulates the disclosure of information related to sustainable development for listed companies. The endpoint in the research period is 2020, as this is the last fiscal year disclosed by listed companies at the time of the research.

Variables measuring

Measuring financial performance: In the research, the author employs ROA to measure FP because, according to Velte (2017), ROA is the typical variable that shows the profitability of a firm's total assets. Moreover, in research related to social responsibility and sustainable development, ROA is often used when considering FP (Velte, 2017).

CEO power: According to Finkelstein's classification, the CEO power construction consists of three dimensions: structural power, expert power, and prestige power. The authors believe that CEOs who are also financial and accounting experts can significantly influence disclosure strategies; so they should use their reputational power, including financial and accounting expertise, to measure the power of CEOs (Artamevia et al., 2024). Therefore, we argue that CEOs with master's degrees or higher in accounting, finance, and business administration have enough power to influence disclosure strategies.

SDID score (SDIDI): SDID score is the overall score of 50 criteria collected through the unweighted content analysis method based on the criteria of GRI 4.0 related to 6 aspects of sustainable development: environment, energy, employees, community, products and sustainable development. If a business publishes the contents in the report, it is recorded as "1", and if it does not publish the contents, it is recorded as "0". The total score for the disclosure of information related to SDID is the sum of all the scores for each item in the sustainability or social responsibility report. Then, the disclosure index SDID will be computed by dividing the overall score of each enterprise by the total number of required disclosure indicators. SDIDI_j takes a value

from 0 to 1, representing the level of disclosure related to the disclosure of information on sustainable development.

$$SDIDI_j = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n x_{ij}}{n_j}$$

Where: *SDIDI_j*: Sustainability development information disclosure index of *j* enterprise and takes values from 0 to 1. If the *SDIDI* value is higher, the level of information disclosure about sustainable development will be higher.

Control variables: In addition to minimising endogeneity problems due to missing variables, the study used firm size, financial leverage, audit quality, and board characteristics as control variables in the research model.

Research model

To examine whether CEO power changes the impact of *SDID* on *FP*, the study established models to measure the impact of each aspect of sustainable development and the overall sustainable development index as well as establish a model with the moderating role of CEO power:

Model 1: $FP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 * SDID_{it} + \beta_2 * BIG4 + \beta_3 * LEV + \beta_4 * SIZE_{it} + \beta_5 * BDIN_{it} + \beta_6 * BDSIZE_{it} + \beta_7 * BDGEN_{it} + \beta_8 * DUAL_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$

Model 2: $FP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 * SDID_{it} + \beta_2 * CEOPOW_{it} + \beta_3 * SDID * CEOPOW_{it} + \beta_4 * BIG4 + \beta_5 * LEV + \beta_6 * SIZE_{it} + \beta_7 * BDIN_{it} + \beta_8 * BDSIZE_{it} + \beta_9 * BDGEN_{it} + \beta_{10} * DUAL_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$

Research Results and Discussion

First, the study conducted a statistical analysis of variables with the results shown in Table 1, showing that the *FP* of companies is relatively low, with a return on total assets of only about 8%. Some companies operate with a very negative profit margin (-0.416), but there are also companies with a pretty high return on assets (over 80%). Furthermore, the publication level of sustainability information from 2020 to 2023 remains relatively low, with an average of approximately 45% of the published criteria. Some companies disclose all 100% of the criteria, while others disclose only 2% of the criteria. This shows that the level of compliance with sustainability disclosure between companies has a quite large difference.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics results of variables

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. dev.	Min	Max
ROA	1.243	0.079	0.082	-0.416	0.817
SDID	1.243	0.454	0.207	0.02	1
LEV	1.243	0.468	0.209	0.004	1.294
SIZE	1.243	12.42	0.609	11.414	14.824
BIG4	1.243	0.390	0.487	0	1
BDIN	1.243	0.228	0.152	0	0.8
BDSIZE	1.243	5.721	1.411	3	12
DUAL	1.243	0.012	0.109	0	1
BDGEN	1.243	0.351	0.327	0	1

Note: *ROA*: return on assets, *SDID*: sustainable development information disclosure. *LEV*: financial leverage measured by the total amount of debts divided by the sum of all assets. *SIZE*

represents the logarithm of total assets. *BIG4* is the dummy variable that holds the value of 1 if a Big Four firm audits the corporation; otherwise, it takes the value of 0. *BDIN* measures the ratio of independent members over the number of members in the board of directors. *BDSIZE* is the total number of members in the board of directors (*BOD*). *DUAL* is a dummy variable that holds the value of 1 if the CEO is also the chairman of the *BOD*. *BDGEN* is a dummy variable that takes the value of 1 if the *BOD* has a female member; otherwise, it takes the value of 0.

Source: Author processed from Stata 17 software

Second, we examined the correlation and multicollinearity between variables. The test results are presented in Table 2. All the correlation coefficients are lower than 0.4, and the VIF coefficient is less than 2 for all variables, indicating that the variables are not closely correlated and there is no multicollinearity phenomenon. Therefore, the model has sufficient predictive value.

Table 2: Check for correlation and multicollinearity

	ROA	SDID	SIZE	BIG4	LEV	BDIN	BDSIZE	DUAL	BDGEN	CEOEXP	VIF
ROA	1										
SDID	0.027	1									1.07
	0.339										
SIZE	-	0.236	1								1.67
	0.025	0.000									
BIG4	0.105	0.121	0.425	1							1.26
	0.000	0.000	0.000								
LEV	-0.33	0.063	0.334	0.01	1						1.18
	0.000	0.027	0.000	0.719							
BDIN	-	-	0.109	0.021	-	1					1.03
	0.058	0.028	0.000	0.455	0.003						
BDSIZE	0.089	0.031	0.344	0.155	0.022	0.102	1				1.17
	0.001	0.272	0.000	0.000	0.430	0.000					
DUAL	-	-	-0.009	-0.028	-	-0.030	-0.046	1			1
	0.043	0.011	0.753	0.324	0.006	0.289	0.105				
BDGEN	-0.05	0.057	0.009	-0.028	-	0.056	-0.052	-0.017	1		1.02
	0.057	0.043	0.743	0.316	0.046	0.046	0.068	0.535			
CEOEXP	-	-	0.063	0.022	-	0.005	0.074	0.017	-0.027	1	1.01
	0.049	0.011	0.026	0.43	0.023	0.418	0.008	0.539	0.334		
MEAN VIF											1.16

Source: Author processed from Stata 17 software

However, in this study, there may be a causal relationship between SDID and FP, so there may be endogeneity. In the study of Li et al. (2018), the endogeneity problem was handled by using the 2SLS (Heckman two-stage estimation procedure) two-step regression. Therefore, in this study, the

author uses the instrument variable of the average annual sample price of SDID with the view that other companies in the same industry may create competitive pressure, forcing them to improve SDID. However, the average SDID score of the industry does not directly impact the performance of a specific firm. Moreover, lag 1 of SDID is also used as an instrument variable for the suspected endogenous variable SDID. Therefore, the study performs a 2SLS regression and conducts endogenous variable tests (estat endog), weak instrumental variable tests (estat firststage), and valid instrumental variable tests (estat overid) in turn. The 2SLS regression results and tests presented in Table 3 indicate that SDID is not an endogenous variable; the instrument variable is the average SDID, and the lagged variable is Lag1. SDID is not a weak instrument; it is a reasonable one. Therefore, the OLS regression remains reliable enough to support the argument.

Table 3: OLS regression and 2SLS regression

ROA	Model 1 (OLS)	Model 1 (2SLS)	Model 2 (OLS)	Model 2 (2SLS)
			roa	roa
SDID	0.0116	0.00528	-0.0134	-0.0202
	[1.11]	[0.39]	(-0.85)	(-0.89)
SIZE	0.00461	0.00553	0.00551	0.00662
	[1.00]	[1.02]	-1.2	-1.22
BIG4	0.0129***	0.0158***	0.0126**	0.0152***
	[2.59]	[2.70]	-2.54	-2.61
LEV	-0.137***	-0.141***	-0.139***	-0.143***
	[-12.20]	[-10.77]	(-12.38)	(-10.97)
BDIN	-0.0372**	-0.0431**	-0.0374***	-0.0434**
	[-2.58]	[-2.54]	(-2.60)	(-2.57)
BDSIZE	0.00432***	0.00477**	0.00451***	0.00500***
	[2.60]	[2.48]	-2.72	-2.61
DUAL	-0.0316	-0.0398	-0.0327*	-0.044
	[-1.59]	[-1.35]	(-1.65)	(-1.50)
BDGEN	-0.0158**	-0.0182**	-0.0166**	-0.0193***
	[-2.37]	[-2.48]	(-2.50)	(-2.64)
CEOEXP			-0.0297***	-0.0338**
			(-2.98)	(-2.55)
SDID *CEOEXP			0.0404**	0.0423
			-2.06	-1.62
_cons	0.0658	0.0578	0.073	0.0647
	[1.29]	[0.96]	-1.43	-1.08
N	1.243	1.243	1.243	1.243
R-sq	0.147	0.156	0.147	0.158
Endogenous test Wu – Hausman			P=0.7930>0.05	P=0.8724>0.05
Weak Instrumental Variable Test (estat firststage)			1940.52>19.93	817.773>19.93
Testing the validity of instrumental variables (Basmann chi2(1))			P=0.1695 >0.05	P=0.1525>0.05

Source: Author processed from Stata 17 software

For model 1, there is a positive correlation between the sustainability disclosure score and financial performance, but it is not statistically significant. This means that the move in disclosure of sustainability does not affect financial performance through the ROA variable. This result rejects hypothesis H1 and is also inconsistent with the findings of previous studies (Chang & Lee, 2022; Wu et al., 2022; Duan et al., 2023; Chen et al., 2023). This research result aligns with the view of information disclosure in Vietnam, an emerging economy where companies have not consistently disclosed information on sustainable development in accordance with their nature.

For model 2, CEO power has resulted in a positive impact on the relationship between SDID and financial performance at the 5% significance level. This result provides empirical evidence that CEOs with expertise in finance and accounting possess a substantial understanding of the role of information, and they may employ strategies for information disclosure to enhance the firm's reputation and prestige, thereby meeting the requirements of stakeholders. They can demonstrate their responsibility to society while not affecting the firm's profit targets. This outcome aligns with the notion that powerful CEOs have greater control and influence in business management activities (Chu et al., 2023), which in turn significantly impacts sustainability information disclosure (Li et al., 2018). Additionally, the two models mentioned exhibit an impact of the control variables on financial performance: BDSIZE and Big4 have a positive influence on ROA, while LEV, BDIN, and BDGEN have a negative correlation with financial performance through ROA. This result suggests that companies with numerous board members or those audited by the Big Four are likely to achieve a higher return on assets, thereby enhancing their financial performance. Companies that use much debt will reduce their profits or financial performance due to the high cost of capital. Additionally, independent members and female members on the BOD have not effectively fulfilled their supervisory role, resulting in a lack of evidence of this impact on FP.

Conclusion

A quantitative study was conducted to investigate the role of CEO power in influencing the relationship between sustainability disclosure and financial performance in Vietnam, an emerging country. At the same time, the study examined the endogeneity issue through 2SLS regression with appropriate tests that acknowledge that all variables in the model are exogenous. Therefore, the study provides reliable evidence that CEOs with strong knowledge and skills in accounting and finance play a crucial role in enhancing the positive impact of sustainability disclosure on financial performance. From these results, the study provides reliable evidence and offers guidance to listed companies on how to enhance their prestige and reputation while maintaining or increasing financial performance. Listed companies may have a policy of recruiting senior leaders – typically directors with specific conditions, including those related to expertise, qualifications, and experience. Financial and accounting expertise may be a priority because, according to this study, it helps senior leaders understand accounting policies, the role of information, and the characteristics of strategies related to sustainable development. In addition, listed companies also need to recognise that audit quality can clearly improve financial performance.

Although the study has attempted to address possible endogeneity issues in the study by using multiple control variables in the research model, as well as conducting related endogeneity tests, the study has not considered the impact of climate change, carbon emissions, political institutions, etc, on financial performance, so the study has not yet provided a comprehensive picture of financial performance. Therefore, future studies should further assess the factors related to climate change, carbon emissions, and political institutions, and enhance the study of other CEO characteristics when examining sustainability disclosure and financial performance to explore this issue in more detail.

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